

ANCIENT LIFE IN THE WAKE OF CRETACEOUS VOLCANISM: INSIGHTS FROM PARANÁ-ETENDEKA WET PEPPERITES

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RESUMO – The dynamic interplay between lava and subaqueous sediments during the early Cretaceous Paraná-Etendeka volcanism in Brazil has revealed a rich ancient life in unconventional settings. This study explores the biodiversity of the Paraná basin, focusing on wet peperites—volcanoclastic rocks formed by the interaction of lava and submerged sediments. Our investigation spans diverse formations within the PE large igneous province, including the Torres, Esmeralda, Pitanga, and Paranapanema. This study unveils the existence of life within the PE deposits, providing vital insights into regional paleoclimatic transitions influenced by volcanic activity. A total of 42 organic walled microfossils (OWM) were recovered from wet peperites, notably *bissacates* exhibiting preserved morphological ornamentation. The upper formations, documenting later stages of the volcanic event, displayed heightened abundance and preservation quality of microfossils, with macrosized dubiofossils identified in the Paranapanema formation. Intriguingly, irregular stem branching in these fossils hints at a potential botanical affiliation, warranting further investigation. Wet peperites stand out for superior fossil preservation and higher microfossil abundance compared to their counterparts, the volcanoclastic heterolytic sandstones. The observed trend suggests early diagenetic differences, possibly accelerated sediment cementation through vapor film generation during the interaction of lava and wet sediments. Our findings extend beyond microfossils, encompassing the first paleontological evidence of organic-walled microfossils, including pollen grains, spores, sporomorphs, acritarchs, and unidentified organic remains, extracted from wet peperites in the PE intertraps. These microfossil assemblages contribute to understanding the extinct biodiversity during the Early Cretaceous, marked by intense magmatism and a regional paleoclimatic transition. Moreover, dubiofossils discovered in association with wet peperites add a layer of complexity to the study. This dubiofossil challenges conventional expectations and underscores the intricate interplay of volcanoclastic interactions within the Paraná-Etendeka large igneous province.

Key-words: Microfossils, Dubiofossils; Volcanism.